

Deliverable 4.5: Young Oncologist Workshop

Young Oncologist Award

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
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Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports);
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web);

Executive summary

The scientific event Young Oncologist Workshop organized by the Slovak Cancer Research Foundation (SCRF), in close cooperation with BMC SAV, a coordinator of the VISION project, was organized in 2020 and 2022. The mission of this event is to bring together young people interested in cancer research and allow them to present their knowledge, ideas, and experimental data to the members of the Scientific Committee. In addition, the workshop allows the participants to acquire new skills in presenting their work in front of the experts and answering questions from the audience. Furthermore, the participants have a unique opportunity to meet other young people with similar interests and discuss their work and results with renowned scientists.

1 Description of this scientific event

The competition Young Oncologist Workshop is held in four categories: 1. Students of the secondary school, 2. Undergraduate students, 3. Ph.D. Students, and 4. Post-docs up to 35 years.

The participant must submit the abstract electronically at least ten days before the event. The members of the Scientific Committee review each abstract before being accepted for presentation. The abstract has to fulfill the following criteria: i) the topic of the presented work must be from the oncology field (it can deal with basic, translational, or clinical research, or it can be a theoretical review), and ii) it have to cover state-of-the-art topics. The Scientific Committee reserves the right to refuse an abstract that does not meet the criteria.

After the conference, all contributions are published *in extenso* in the peer-reviewed Proceeding with ISBN; the publisher is SCRF. The conference/workshop is free of charge.

In each category, SCRF awards the three best presentations selected by the Scientific Committee with monetary or in-kind prizes.

1.1 Young Oncologist Workshop 2020

In 2020, Young Oncologist Workshop took place in Žilina, Slovakia, on March 9 – 10. That year, Ph.D. students from VISION partner institutions - from Greece (NKUA) and Spain (IRYCIS) also registered for the competition, increasing the credit and recognition of this event. Abstracts prepared by these students can be found at <http://vision.sav.sk/presentations.html>. The online presentations can be found in the Education Activities section of the VISION website.

However, due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic at the beginning of 2020 and the uncertain/unpredictable epidemiological situation and related travel restrictions in Slovakia, SCRF decided to cancel the event.

More information at <https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/sutaz-mladych-onkologov-2020-2/> (in Slovak)

1.2 Young Oncologist Workshop 2022

The competition Young Oncologist Workshop was performed online on March 7 – 8, 2022. In contrast to the previous event, the competition was organized only in 3 categories, 1. Undergraduate students, 2. Ph.D. students, and 3. Post-docs up to 35 years.

In total, 25 competitors registered, among them 2 in category 1, 19 in category 2, and 5 in category 3. Eight participants were from abroad; from VISION partner institutions - there were 4 participants (1 in the category of Undergraduate students and 3 in the category of Ph.D. students) from Spain (IRYCIS); and 2 participants (all in the category of Ph.D. students) from Greece (NKUA). From BMC SAV, there were 11 participants (8 in the category of Ph.D. students and 3 in the category of post-docs up to 35 years). The other participants were from Slovak universities. Each participant received a certificate of attendance.

Example of the Certificate of attendance

The awards ceremony was held in person on April 20, 2022, in Bratislava, Slovakia. The president of SCRF, Margita Klobušická, Ph.D., presented the prizes to the winners.

Winner in the category of Ph.D. students
Maria Urbanova

Winner in the category of post-docs
Jana Plava, Ph.D.

Young Oncologist Award 2022 winners

(From left to right: Lajos Gergely, Lenka Trnkova, Eva Kocianova, Nataliia Nikolaieva, Natalia Udvorkova, Jana Plava, Maria Urbanova)

Photos by: Gabriela Pavlikova, SCRF

The Young Oncologist Award 2022 results, including the abstracts in Slovak or English, are published on the SCRF website (<https://www.nvr.sk/akcie/2022-young-oncologist-award-results/>).

1.2.1 List of the winners

- **Category Undergraduate students**

- **Category Ph.D. students**

- Category post-docs up to 35 years

Heartfelt congratulations to the Young Oncologist Award 2022 winners.

2 Deviation from the workplan

Due to the coronavirus pandemic, the Young Oncologist Workshop had to be canceled in 2020. In 2022, the Young Oncologist Workshop was held online to prevent unpredictable situations if the epidemic situation of COVID-19 suddenly worsened. However, the awards ceremony took place in person on April 20, 2022, in Bratislava, Slovakia.

3 Conclusion

The Young Oncologist Workshop is an attractive event for young talented people interested in cancer research. It is an excellent opportunity for them to acquire new skills in presenting their results and ideas in front of experts from different fields of oncology. In addition, this event is a good starting point for their future personal and professional development.